

HEALTH CARE ACCESSIBILITY FOR INDIVIDUALS WITH DISABILITIES: BARRIERS AND RISK FACTORS IMPACTING CARE

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BACKGROUND

Healthcare professionals have certain professional, legal, and ethical obligations that they must fulfill with each patient interaction. Though professional and legal obligations may vary between fields of practice, the core ethical responsibility remains the same: provide just health care¹. This requires that healthcare professionals are aware of systemic and institutional factors that lead to disparity and discrimination in the provision of health services¹. Disability is a complex construct that can be related to various factors related to health condition as well as social and environmental factors that influence participation. This complexity results in varying definitions; the ICF model of disability was used in this research².

Figure 1. ICF Framework²

METHODS

Inclusion Criteria:

- Health care in the United States
- Individuals with a physical disability or limitation
- Discussion of disparity and accessibility related to the provision of healthcare
- Publication date of January 1, 2014 or later
- Data from 2010 or later
- Age 18 and older

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies irrelevant to health care in the United States
- Individuals with a mental disability or hard of hearing
- Specialty care irrelevant to the purposes of this study
- Pediatric patient population
- Full text not available.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS: ACCESS BARRIERS

Figure 2. Commonly cited barriers preventing access to healthcare evaluated in current literature^{3,5-8,10-12,15,20-21}

PRELIMINARY RESULTS: RISK FACTORS

Figure 3. Commonly cited risk factors potentially resulting in healthcare disparity evaluated in current literature^{3,5, 8-11,13-14,16-22.}

LIMITATION

- Non-homogenous populations
- Varying data sources.

DISCUSSION

Disparity in the provision of health care is not a new topic of discussion; however, past research has primarily focused on age, racial/ethnic, and socioeconomic disparities related to health care. Recently, arguments have been made that people with disability also experience disparity in the receipt of health care services.

This research sought to compile the most commonly cited factors that are thought to factor into this inequality. Despite the implementation of various legislative measures including the Americans with Disability Act and, more recently, the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act, disparity still exists in the provision of health care. The most commonly cited barriers include transportation^{5,7,9-11,14,19-20}, care coordination^{4-5,9-11,14}, and physical access to a health care provider^{7,10-11,14,19-20}. Certain groups are more likely to experience these barriers to care, the most commonly cited significant factors being age^{9-10,13,15-16,19,21}, race/ethnicity^{9,12-13,15-21}, and gender^{10,15,18-19}.

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